

CONSENT FORM FOR STUDENTS AND PARENT(S)

Information notice on research project STEMCo and processing of personal data

Dear parent(s) and student,

Eurac Research – a private, not-for-profit research center in Bolzano, Italy – is conducting research within the European project “STEMCo” (Stances Toward Education in Multilingual Contexts), funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation. Your child’s school and class have been selected as potential participants in this project. With this document, we inform you about the project, its data and privacy management, and the types of data collected in the project “STEMCo”. **We ask you to read this document carefully and sign the last pages. A simplified explanation has also been provided to ensure comprehension. Participation is entirely voluntary.**

The staff of the project thanks you for your collaboration and contribution. For further information, please contact the researcher, Andrea Leone-Pizzighella, e-mail: aleonepizzighella@eurac.edu, tel.

I. Research project

STEMCo aims to further our understanding of how multilingualism is accommodated, encouraged, and/or managed in middle schools. The objective of this research activity is to observe ongoing classroom practices, reflect on them with teachers, identify teaching approaches for accommodating and fostering multilingualism in middle schools, and to develop training materials for teachers at your child’s school, throughout Italy and, eventually, throughout Europe.

This project has six phases, only the first four of which will take place in direct collaboration with your child’s school during the **2022-2023 school year**. Should your child participate in this project, he/she will be asked to take part in surveys, participant observation, recording, and interviews (see below for details).

1) Surveys

The researcher will ask participants to complete one or two very brief surveys (about 5 questions) prior to and during the academic year. These surveys will ask student participants to share their age, the languages they speak, the city they live in, and the occupations of their parents. The surveys for teachers will ask their age, the languages they speak, the city they live in, and their professional background. Email addresses for all participants will be requested for the purpose of administering surveys via Survey Monkey (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/legal/privacy/>). **The results of these surveys will be pseudonymized when archived and anonymized if shared externally.**

2) Participant observation and recording

The researcher will observe second-year classes once or twice a week throughout the 2022-2023 academic year and will take notes, audio- and video-record lessons, and gather examples of student work, worksheets, photos of textbook pages, etc. **The identity of all student participants will remain confidential when data are shared publicly. Data used for the scope of teacher training at your child’s school will be pseudonymized. See table on page 5 for details.**

3) Interviews

The researcher will occasionally conduct brief interviews with both teachers and students over the course of the academic year. These interviews will be conducted during free moments throughout the school day and will not interrupt class time. **Any interview data shared publicly or for the purposes of teacher training will be anonymized.**

4) Workshops with teachers

Data collected from surveys and interviews will be anonymized by the researcher. Video recordings will be pseudonymized by the application of a visual filter (see page 6 for examples). These data will

be used in teacher training workshops for teachers **at your child's school** as a means of facilitating reflection on their teaching practice, specifically regarding students' multilingualism and language use in general. These workshops will be audio-visually recorded for further analysis in (5) and for the creation of teacher training materials in (6). These workshops may then lead to minor changes in teachers' classroom practice which have the scope of understanding and fostering the diversity of ways in which students communicate.

**In the event that schools must switch to e-learning format, (2), (3), and (4) will be conducted online via [Zoom](#) or [Microsoft Teams](#).*

5) Analysis of data and presentation of results for academic audiences and the general public

Anonymized data from (1), (2), (3), and (4) will be analyzed for academic conferences and publications. Selections of pseudonymized data will also be made available via an Open Access database for teachers and language researchers, such as TalkBank. Selections of anonymized data will also be made available via an Open Access repository such as CLARIN. Small selections of anonymized data may also be presented at school community events and at venues for the general public, such as Eurac's website, blog, or social media accounts. See table on page 5 for further details on pseudonymization and anonymization.

For more information about Open Access science: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

For more information about TalkBank: <https://talkbank.org/>

For more information about CLARIN: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/repositories>

6) Adaptation of data for creation of teacher training materials

Pseudonymized data from (1), (2), (3), and (4) will also be adapted for use in teacher training materials such as online courses, seminars, and workshops. The aim of these trainings is to facilitate accommodation of multilingualism and communicative differences in middle school communities.

Benefits and risks related to participation

Your child's participation is 100% voluntary. Your child may not receive direct benefits for participating in this study, but this study may help improve the education of students like your child by giving teachers insight into the experiences that have shaped who your child is in the classroom today and the ways he/she participates in schooling. **Participants in STEMCo incur minimal risk.** If you provide consent below, we may use a pseudonymized recording of your child for training and research purposes. Your child will never be identified directly (e.g., by name or other identifiable personal data) if we play part of these data for anyone outside of your child's school. All documents containing identifying information and all audio recordings will be stored securely at Eurac Research. If you do not consent, we will not record them and we will do everything possible to keep your child's identity confidential throughout the research process.

II. Data Privacy Statement

In accordance with current data protection regulations, we hereby provide you with information about how the data of minors is processed. All personal data is dealt with in compliance with EU Regulation No. 2016/679 (GDPR) and the national legislation. The processing of personal data by researchers is based on principles of integrity, legality, transparency, and confidentiality.

1. Data Controller and Data Protection Officer (DPO)

Data Controller: Eurac Research, Viale Druso 1, 39100 Bolzano, in the person of its legal representative; You can contact the DPO under the following e-mail address:

privacy@eurac.edu.

2. Purpose and Legal Basis for the Data Processing

Any and all personal data that is in the possession of the Controller, or that may be requested by the Controller, is necessary for the following purposes:

- Participation in the research study and thus use of the data for research purposes, as specified under point I;
- communications by e-mail (including sending links to surveys);
- documentation of data for archival purposes (concerning data revealing the person's image and voice, e.g. video, audio, photographic recordings). Any images of your child that are publicly presented at training events, conferences, or other events will use a filter that obscures your child's face.

In order not to be filmed or recorded during classroom observations, students may make their request to the researcher either ahead of time or in the moment of the recording (either in writing or via spoken request). The wishes of any parents and/or students who state that they do not want to be recorded at any time throughout the study will be respected.

The personal data that are processed are specified under point I. Within the framework of the project, special categories of personal data may also be processed in accordance with Art. 9 GDPR (such as data revealing racial or ethnic origins, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, sexual orientation). The ethnographic and long-term nature of this project means that such personal details may come to light over time, even if they are not sought out by the researcher, and may consequently become part of the archive of data for the project. **This does not mean that such data will appear in analyses.** Sensitive categories of data that are necessary to the interpretation of data will appear only in entirely anonymized and aggregated form when analyses are presented to the public.

The legal basis for the processing of your personal data for the purposes indicated above is your consent to the processing of your personal data (art. 6, par. 1, lett. A and art. 9, par. 2, lett. A). Such data may be redacted at any point, upon request of the participant and regardless of initial consent to participate.

3. Recipients of the Data Processed and Transfer of Data

The recipients of the data are the scientific employees of the Institute of Applied Linguistics at Eurac Research and persons in charge of data processing activities, authorized and instructed by the data controller to data processing activities. Personal data may be communicated to external service providers (e.g. sending e-mails and analyzing the functional capability of the website), which typically process Personal Data on behalf of Eurac Research as data processors.

The scientific results (e.g. publications of scientific papers) may be disseminated only in aggregated and anonymized form, or rather in such a manner that it is impossible identify the individuals. As mentioned above, the data collected for STEMCo will be used for the creation of Open Access teacher training materials (courses, guides, classroom materials). Selected data (e.g., excerpts of recorded classroom discourse and their associated transcripts) will also be made available in anonymized form on an Open Access platform such as CLARIN or in a pseudonymized form on TalkBank (see links above for more information).

For questionnaires Eurac Research uses Survey Monkey (for further information: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/legal/privacy/>).

To provide certain services Eurac Research and the Free University of Bolzano manage together the scientific platform Scientific Network South Tyrol which connects their data centers. Eurac Research and the Free University of Bolzano are Joint Controllers of the personal data processed in this context and, accordingly, have entered into an agreement pursuant to art. 26 of the GDPR.

Your child's data is stored within the European Union and Eurac Research does not intend to transfer this data to third countries or international organisations. Some personal data could be transmitted to third countries outside of the EU but only if the transmission of personal data is connected to the

performance of the institutional activities of Eurac Research. Where data is transferred to a third country, this will be done on the basis of the European Commission's standard contractual clauses (SCC) with supplementary measures and in accordance with the legal requirements.

4. Information on the Retention Period of Personal Data

Untreated or "raw" personal data will be stored no longer than for the time strictly necessary to achieve the purposes indicated, or for a period not exceeding 36 months, and in any case in order to comply with the Applicable Law (Artt.2946-2947). At the end of this period, the untreated data shall be deleted, with only the pseudonymized selections of data remaining on TalkBank and selections of aggregated/anonymous data remaining on CLARIN.

5. Mandatory or Voluntary Communication of Data and Possible Consequences of a Failure to Provide it

The provision of personal data is voluntary, but refusal could interfere with the correct performance of the purposes, thus rendering the participation in the project impossible. There are no consequences for your child should he/she choose not to participate in this research project.

6. Automated Decision-Making Processes

There are no automated decision-making processes that could produce an adverse legal effect on the participant or have a similarly significant negative impact upon them.

7. The Participant's Rights

At any time the participant has the right to request access to their personal data, and to correct or delete that data, or to limit its processing. In addition, the participant retains the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory. When the data processing is based on consent, the participant has the right to withdraw that consent at any time. The participant may also exercise all other rights pursuant to current data protection regulations (art. 15 et seq. GDPR) by writing to the e-mail address: privacy@eurac.edu.

SIMPLE SUMMARY:

What is this project? The goal of this project (STEMCo) is to learn from interactions between students and teachers so that we can help new teachers learn how to work more effectively with multilingual students and in multilingual contexts.

Who is the researcher? Andrea Leone-Pizzighella is an American linguistic anthropologist of education who works as a postdoctoral researcher at Eurac Research.

When does the research start and how long does it last? The research for this project will last the entire 2022-2023 school year. The researcher will visit your class once or twice a week.

What kind of research will be done? STEMCo is a participatory action research project, which means that the researcher will work together with teachers to think about the way they teach and learn how to be even more effective. To do this, the researcher will observe your classes, record them, interview you, and take notes. The researcher and your teachers will look over these data together and study them. Then, we'll see how we can find more or better ways to accommodate language differences in your school.

What do I have to do if I participate in this research? You don't need to do anything special aside from letting the researcher film and audio-record your classes and ask you questions occasionally. If you don't want to be recorded, that's fine. You do not have to participate in this project if you don't want to. If you decide to participate at first, and then you change your mind, that's also fine. Whether you participate or not, your identity will be kept confidential.

PARENT(S)/GUARDIAN(S) and STUDENTS, please read the last two pages carefully and check the appropriate boxes.

	Fieldnotes	Surveys	Audio Recordings	Video Recordings	Transcripts	Photos	Student Work
Identifying information included in each category of data	<i>Names, personal data, possibly special categories of personal data</i>	<i>Names, personal data</i>	<i>Names, voices, personal data, possibly special categories of personal data</i>	<i>Names, voices, faces, personal data, possibly special categories of personal data</i>	<i>Possibly personal data and special categories of personal data</i>	<i>Faces, names</i>	<i>Names, handwriting</i>
Private archive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data ✓ (possibly) special categories of personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ names ✓ voices ✓ personal data ✓ special categories of personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ names ✓ faces ✓ voices ✓ personal data ✓ special categories of personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data ✓ (possibly) special categories of personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ faces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ handwriting
Open Access archive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * special categories of personal data ✓ personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data <p>AGGREGATED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * voices * special categories of personal data ✓ personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ handwriting
Teacher training at research site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data <p>AGGREGATED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * voices * special categories of personal data * personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ handwriting
Public presentations and publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data <p>"AGGREGATED"</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data <p>AGGREGATED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * voices * special categories of personal data * personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ handwriting
Open Access teacher training materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data <p>"AGGREGATED"</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ personal data <p>AGGREGATED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces * personal data * special categories of personal data ✓ voices <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * voices * special categories of personal data * personal data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names * faces <p>VISUAL FILTER APPLIED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * names ✓ handwriting

* indicates that these data will not be included

✓ indicates that these data will be included

Example of visual filters that will be applied to publicly available video or photographic data:

image source: <https://www.learninghowtolookandlisten.com/>

**PLEASE SIGN AND RETURN PAGES 7 and 8 TO THE RESEARCHER.
KEEP THE OTHER PAGES AS A REFERENCE.**

I. CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN THE PROJECT

I, the undersigned _____, parent/guardian of _____, class _____, school _____

DECLARE to have understood the contents and objectives of STEMCo and

- CONSENT**
 DO NOT CONSENT

to my child's participation in this project. I understand that my consent may be revoked in writing at any time without giving reasons, with the consequence that the data may no longer be used. Publications that have already taken place are not affected by the revocation.

Place, date _____ Signature _____

STUDENTS, PLEASE CIRCLE THE APPROPRIATE SELECTION AND SIGN YOUR NAME BELOW.

I, _____, **ASSENT / DO NOT ASSENT** to participate in this project.

Place, date _____ Signature _____

II. CONSENT TO THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

The Undersigned **DECLARES** to have read the Information about personal data handling and is aware of this notice as drawn up pursuant to UE Reg. 2016/679 and national legislation and

- CONSENTS**
 DOES NOT CONSENT

to the processing of his/her child's personal data, including any special categories of personal data in accordance with Art. 9 GDPR (such as data revealing racial or ethnic origins) provided to the researcher. I understand that my child may strike data from the record, via spoken request, at any time.

Place, date _____ Signature _____

STUDENTS, PLEASE CIRCLE THE APPROPRIATE SELECTION AND SIGN YOUR NAME BELOW.

I, _____, **ASSENT / DO NOT ASSENT** to the processing of my personal data.

Place, date _____ Signature _____

III. AUDIO AND VIDEO RECORDING AUTHORIZATION FORM

The undersigned authorizes hereby, according to art. 96 and 97 l. n. 633/1941 (Copyright law) Eurac Research (and any person acting under the authority of Eurac Research) to the following forms of recording throughout the research phase of STEMCo:

Do you consent to the audio- and videorecording of your child's classes and their use for pedagogical and research purposes?

YES

NO

Do you consent to the publication of pseudonymized audio and video data of your child on an Open Access platform, free of charge, for an unlimited period of time? (see pages 5 and 6 for more information)

YES

NO

The undersigned declares that he/she will have no claims against Eurac Research with respect to the above and waives all rights, claims and/or actions arising out of the present authorization.

Place, date _____

Signature _____

STUDENTS, PLEASE CIRCLE THE APPROPRIATE SELECTION AND SIGN YOUR NAME BELOW.

I, _____, **ASSENT / DO NOT ASSENT** to the audio and videorecording of my classes.

Place, date _____

Signature _____

Please feel free to add any further questions or requests for the researcher or the school principal below.

In the case of minor participants and, therefore, the processing of the personal data of minors, specific consent and authorization will be requested from the person exercising parental authority and/or the holder of parental responsibility as provided for by art. 8 GDPR. In the event that only one parent signs, he/she declares that he/she is aware that he/she is also expressing the will of the other parent who exercises parental responsibility - aware of the administrative and criminal consequences for those who issue declarations that do not correspond to the truth pursuant to Presidential Decree 245/2000, he/she declares that he/she has made the choice in compliance with the provisions on parental responsibility set out in Articles 316, 337 ter and 337 quater of the Civil Code, which require the consent of both parents.